

FACTORS INFLUENCING WORK MOTIVATION OF GRASSROOTS-LEVEL OFFICIALS OF THE VIETNAM WOMEN'S UNION

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the factors that influence the work motivation of grassroots-level officials of the Vietnam Women's Union (VWU) in the Red River Delta region of Vietnam. The research is grounded in several foundational theories, including Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964), Adams' Equity Theory (1965), and the Public Service Motivation (PSM) theory developed by Perry et al. (1990). The factors considered in the study include: compensation, working environment, job characteristics, performance evaluation and recognition, training and promotion opportunities, and contribution to the community and society. These six factors are hypothesized to influence work motivation both directly and indirectly through the mediating role of job satisfaction. The study employed "a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques. Primary data were collected from a survey of 899 grassroots-level VWU officials in the Red River Delta region and analyzed using AMOS software "and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The empirical results indicate that all six factors included in the model exert both direct and indirect effects—via job satisfaction—on work motivation, although with varying levels of influence. Among them, the desire to contribute to the community and society emerged as the most influential factor (both directly and indirectly), followed by training and promotion opportunities, and performance evaluation and recognition. Based on the findings, the research team proposes several feasible recommendations and solutions to enhance the work motivation of grassroots-level officials of the Vietnam Women's Union in the Red River Delta region.

Keywords: Influencing Factors; Public Sector Work Motivation; Job Satisfaction; Grassroots Officials; Vietnam Women's Union.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work motivation plays a vital role in enhancing individual and organizational productivity. The primary purpose of motivation is to ensure the optimal use of human resources, leveraging human potential to improve organizational performance continuously. Fostering motivation among employees is therefore crucial to the success and sustainability of organizational operations.

The Vietnam Women's Union (VWU) is a socio-political organization that represents and protects the legitimate rights and interests of women across various social strata. The VWU is tasked with advocating for and supporting women, safeguarding their legal rights and interests, and participating in Party-building and state governance. The dedication, responsibility, dynamism, and creativity of VWU officials significantly contribute to the

advancement of women's movements and the overall effectiveness of the organization's activities.

However, grassroots-level VWU officials currently face numerous challenges, including heavy workloads and limited compensation. These difficulties adversely impact their motivation and work performance. Therefore, identifying the factors that influence the work motivation of grassroots VWU officials, and subsequently proposing effective solutions to enhance that motivation, is a matter of both theoretical importance and practical urgency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH MODEL ON THE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE WORK MOTIVATION OF GRASSROOTS OFFICIALS OF THE VIETNAM WOMEN'S UNION

2.1. Theoretical Foundations

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943): Maslow asserted that human behavior is driven by a hierarchy of internal needs that must be satisfied in a sequential order, from the most basic to higher-level needs.

These include physiological needs, safety, social belonging, esteem, and self-actualization. He conceptualized this into a five-tier pyramid, widely recognized in motivational theory.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959): Herzberg categorized work motivation factors into two groups: hygiene factors and motivator factors. Hygiene factors are external conditions such as organizational policies, salary, benefits, working conditions, job security, and interpersonal relationships.

Motivator factors include achievement, recognition, job responsibility, autonomy, promotion opportunities, and the meaningfulness and challenge of the job.

Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964): Vroom proposed that work motivation arises not only from internal needs but also from the worker's cognitive evaluation of the relationships between effort, performance, and reward. His theory is formalized as:

Motivation = Expectancy × Instrumentality × Valence

Where all three components must be present and high for motivation to be maximized.

Adams' Equity Theory (1965): This theory posits that individuals' motivation is significantly influenced by their subjective perception of fairness in the exchange of effort and reward. Equity does not imply equal distribution of outcomes, but rather proportionality between contributions and returns relative to others.

Public Service Motivation (PSM) Theory – Perry et al. (1990): PSM describes an intrinsic motivation toward serving the public interest, contributing to society, and creating public value, rather than pursuing personal or financial gain. It reflects the value system, ethical commitment, and internal drive specific to public servants.

2.2. Overview of Relevant Studies

2.2.1. Studies on Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction

According to Locke (1976), job satisfaction emerges from the alignment between what employees expect and what they experience.

It reflects the degree of congruence between expectations and reality. Job satisfaction is a key psychological construct that encompasses various aspects of the work environment, such as job content, working conditions, income, social relationships, career development opportunities, recognition, and organizational policies.

Spector (1997) identified nine key job aspects affecting job satisfaction: leadership, colleagues, nature of work, promotion opportunities, policies, working conditions, job security, compensation, and recognition. Among these, relationships with supervisors and colleagues, as well as development opportunities, have a particularly strong influence.

In Vietnam, Tran Kim Dung (2013) confirmed that fairness in evaluation, working conditions, and professional development opportunities strongly affect job satisfaction among public officials.

Vo Tien Si (2021), studying job satisfaction among public officials in Phú Ninh District (Quảng Nam Province), found that salary and welfare significantly influence job satisfaction, though to a lesser extent than job characteristics.

This highlights a real challenge: while many officials are committed to community service, inadequate or inequitable compensation can lead to dissatisfaction, reduced motivation, and organizational detachment.

Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2018) evaluated the impact of seven theoretical factors on job satisfaction among staff at Sóc Trăng Provincial General Hospital. Four factors showed positive influence: (1) Training and promotion, (2) Salary, (3) Welfare, and (4) Peer relationships.

Among these, training and promotion had the strongest effect, surpassing even financial incentives, indicating that sustainable career development is more valued than short-term material rewards among healthcare professionals.

Ha Nam Khanh Giao and Nguyen Thi Nha (2020), in a study on State Treasury officers in Ho Chi Minh City, identified six factors that positively affect job satisfaction (in ascending order): training and promotion, job characteristics, peer relationships, welfare, salary, and supervisors.

Nguyen Danh Nam (2024) explored “the role of salary satisfaction on organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention among frontline healthcare workers in Hanoi. Results indicated that organizational commitment and job satisfaction are positively influenced by salary satisfaction, while turnover intention is primarily affected by welfare benefits.

2.2.2. Studies on Factors Influencing Work Motivation

Maslow (1943) asserted that individuals strive for higher levels of motivation when their basic needs—physiological, safety, esteem, and self-actualization—are met.

McClelland (1985) emphasized motivation as driven by three core needs: achievement, power, and affiliation. Meanwhile, Vroom (1964) posited that people are only motivated when they believe their efforts will lead to desirable outcomes and fair rewards.

Gagné and Deci (2005), through their Self-Determination Theory, found that intrinsic motivation is fostered when individuals feel autonomy in action, competence in work, and relatedness to colleagues and the organization. These factors serve as catalysts for proactive behavior, creativity, and long-term engagement.

In the public sector, Perry and Wise (1990) emphasized that the work environment plays a vital role in sustaining Public Service Motivation (PSM), particularly when it nurtures public values and administrative efficiency.

Wright and Davis (2003) further highlighted that organizational support, including physical conditions and a healthy working environment, strongly correlates with job satisfaction and motivation. Bakker and Demerouti (2007), in their Job Demands–Resources Model, also confirmed that supportive environments—such as well-equipped offices and effective teamwork—boost work engagement and reduce burnout.

In Vietnam, Hoang Manh Dung and Le Bao Hoan (2021), studying civil servants in Ninh Hòa Town (Khánh Hòa Province), identified five factors influencing work motivation (in descending order): (1) Income and welfare, (2) Training and promotion, (3) Work environment, (4) Rewards and recognition, (5) Supervisor support. Income and welfare were found to be the most influential, surpassing other factors such as work environment or recognition.

Tran Kim Dung (2013) concluded that income, working conditions, and human resource development policies are the three pillars of sustainable public sector motivation. Additionally, a survey by Nguyễn Thị Thu Hương and Nguyễn Hữu Lộc (2020) in Ho Chi Minh City confirmed that timely promotion and recognition significantly enhance proactive attitudes, responsibility, and career commitment.

Nguyen Van Dinh, Tran Van Ty, and Cao Thi Sen (2022), in a study conducted in Phong Điền District (Cần Thơ City), identified the working environment as one of six factors influencing motivation, alongside training, peer relationships, and remuneration. Although its impact was less than others, it remains essential for maintaining work performance.

Nguyen Hong Giang and Doan Hoang Lan (2022) also found that access to basic facilities such as computers, internet, and office supplies is crucial for improving task performance and motivation. These findings are consistent with earlier studies by Ha Nam Khanh Giao & Nguyen Tran Bao Ngoc (2018) and Huynh Thi Thu Suong (2017), who affirmed that a positive work environment fosters inspiration, creativity, and organizational commitment.

2.2.3. Studies on the Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Influencing Factors and Work Motivation

According to Hackman and Oldham's Job Characteristics Model (1976), five core job attributes—skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback—affect three psychological states: experienced meaningfulness, experienced responsibility, and knowledge of results. These states, in turn, lead to job satisfaction and subsequently higher work motivation.

Modern public human resource management studies consistently affirm that organizational factors such as compensation, working environment, job characteristics, performance recognition, and development opportunities influence not only job satisfaction but also work motivation (Herzberg, 1959; Vroom, 1964; Judge et al., 2001).

Numerous studies have also confirmed that Public Service Motivation is significantly associated with job satisfaction, organizational commitment, job performance, and reduced turnover in the public sector (Ritz, Brewer & Neumann, 2016; Bellé, 2013; Kim, 2005; Vandenabeele, 2009).

In Vietnam, Le Van Hoa and Nguyen Ngoc Quynh (2021) found that in the public administration sector, job satisfaction reflects not only the alignment between expectations and workplace reality but also serves as a psychological regulator that helps sustain long-term motivation. Mai Ngoc Khuong, Pham Thi Hong Le, and Huynh Phuong Uyên (2022) showed that factors such as training needs assessment, training methods, and content “have a positive impact on job satisfaction, work motivation, and performance among civil servants in Ben Tre Province.

In conclusion, numerous studies affirm that job satisfaction is a precursor to higher work motivation. Accordingly, factors that enhance job satisfaction also indirectly influence motivation. However, there remains a gap in existing literature regarding the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between influencing factors and work motivation among grassroots-level officials of the Vietnam Women's Union.

2.3. Research Model on the Factors Influencing the Work Motivation of Grassroots Women's Union Officials

2.3.1. Proposed Research Model

Based on the theoretical framework and literature review, the author proposes a research model comprising six key factors influencing the work motivation of grassroots-level officials of the Vietnam Women's Union. These include:

(1) Compensation; (2) Working Environment; (3) Job Characteristics; (4) Performance Evaluation and Recognition; (5) Training and Promotion Opportunities; (6) Contribution to the Community and Society.

These factors are hypothesized to exert “both direct and indirect effects on work motivation. The indirect effects operate through the mediating variable of **job satisfaction**.

Figure 1: Proposed Research Model

(Source: Author's Proposal)

2.3.2. Research Hypotheses

- H1:** Compensation has a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.
- H2:** The working environment has a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.
- H3:** Job characteristics have a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.
- H4:** Performance evaluation and recognition have a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.
- H5:** Training and promotion opportunities have a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.
- H6:** The desire to contribute to the community and society has a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.

Job satisfaction is also hypothesized to play a mediating role in the relationship between the identified factors and work motivation. When employees are satisfied, they are more likely to be committed, responsible, and persistent in their roles. This is especially true for Women's Union officials, who are primarily driven by responsibility rather than material benefits. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

- H7:** Compensation positively influences work motivation through the mediating effect of job satisfaction.
- H8:** The working environment positively influences work motivation through the mediating effect of job satisfaction.
- H9:** Job characteristics positively influence work motivation through the mediating effect of job satisfaction.
- H10:** Performance evaluation and recognition positively influence work motivation through the mediating effect of job satisfaction
- H11:** Training and promotion opportunities positively influence work motivation through the mediating effect of job satisfaction.
- H12:** The desire to contribute to the community and society positively influences work motivation through the mediating effect of job satisfaction.

Additionally, the author examines the mediating role of job satisfaction in the overall relationship between influencing factors and work motivation. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

- H13:** Job satisfaction has a positive impact on the work motivation of grassroots Women's Union officials.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Qualitative Research Method

Analytical and synthesis methods were employed to clarify the theoretical foundations related to the factors influencing the work motivation of grassroots-level Women's Union officials.

In addition, the research team conducted semi-structured in-depth interviews with 12 grassroots-level Women's Union officials (including Chairwomen and Vice-Chairwomen of the Union at the commune/ward level) and 3 officials from central/provincial/district levels with extensive experience in personnel and organizational work.

These interviews aimed to explore the perceptions and practical experiences of grassroots Union staff. Furthermore, the author conducted unstructured interviews with 3 experts (PhDs and Associate Professors in public administration) to refine the conceptual framework and identify key influencing factors for the proposed research model. These interviews also provide a robust foundation for developing the survey instrument.

3.2. Quantitative Research Method

3.2.1. Data Collection Method

The study employed survey questionnaires to collect data. In order to test the proposed hypotheses from the research model, the author designed a structured questionnaire and conducted a pilot survey to refine it.

The author collaborated with local Women's Unions to distribute the questionnaire during meetings, conferences, or fieldwork trips. Questionnaires were handed out directly and collected on-site, which allowed for real-time clarification and increased the validity and completion rate of responses. Additionally, the questionnaire was distributed online via Google Forms, with the link shared through Zalo, Facebook, or internal email groups of the Women's Union, provided that consent was obtained from provincial or district-level Union leaders.

Out of 900 distributed questionnaires, 899 valid responses were collected. Due to the purposive sampling approach—where respondents were carefully selected, filtered, and responded directly via Google Forms—all 899 responses “were deemed valid and included in the data analysis.

3.2.2. Data Processing Method

After data collection, the dataset was cleaned and analyzed using AMOS software along with the following analytical techniques:

***Reliability Testing using Cronbach's Alpha:**

The reliability of the measurement scales was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. According to Hoang Trọng & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2008), a Cronbach's Alpha from 0.8 to nearly 1.0 indicates excellent reliability; from 0.7 to 0.8 is acceptable. Hair et al. (1998) suggest that “a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.6 or higher is also acceptable. In this study, scales with a Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.60 were retained for further analysis.

***Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA):**

EFA was employed to explore the interrelationships among variables and to reduce a set of K 's observed variables into a smaller set of F meaningful factors ($F < K$). According to Hair et al. (1998), for sample sizes greater than 350, factor loadings of >0.5 indicate acceptable convergence.” Variables with factor loadings below 0.5 were excluded to ensure scale validity. Furthermore, total variance explained should be $\geq 50\%$ and each factor must have an Eigenvalue ≥ 1 .

The EFA included the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. The KMO index is used to assess the suitability of the data for factor analysis. A KMO value between 0.5 and 1.0 indicates adequacy; values below 0.5 suggest that factor analysis may be inappropriate.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): CFA was conducted to assess the goodness-of-fit between the theoretical model and empirical data. It also provides evidence for

convergent validity and discriminant validity of the latent constructs. The model fit was evaluated using the following indices as suggested by Hair et al. (2010):

- CMIN/df: ≤ 2 (good), ≤ 5 (acceptable)
- CFI (Comparative Fit Index): ≥ 0.90 (good), ≥ 0.95 (very good), ≥ 0.80 (acceptable)
- TLI (Tucker–Lewis Index): ≥ 0.90 (good), ≥ 0.95 (excellent)
- GFI (Goodness of Fit Index): ≥ 0.90 (good), ≥ 0.95 (excellent)
- RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation): ≤ 0.08 (good), ≤ 0.03 (excellent)

***Structural Equation Modeling (SEM):**

SEM was used to describe the relationships among observed and latent variables, primarily for hypothesis testing. SEM integrates multiple techniques, including multiple regression, factor analysis, and path analysis, enabling the examination of complex relationships.

SEM allows simultaneous estimation of all model parameters, including causal relationships among latent constructs, measurement errors, and correlations among residuals. It accommodates both recursive and non-recursive relationships, as well as direct and indirect effects.

Similar to CFA, the SEM model fit was also assessed using the above-mentioned indices to ensure theoretical and empirical validity.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Evaluation of Scale Quality and Reliability

4.1.1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Analysis

The results of Cronbach's Alpha testing for the factors under examination are as follows:

- Compensation: In the first run, item TL1 was removed due to a Corrected Item-Total Correlation < 0.3 . After the second run, the Cronbach's Alpha value reached 0.876.
- Working Environment: 0.875
- Job Characteristics: 0.879
- Performance Evaluation and Recognition: 0.889
- Training and Promotion Opportunities: 0.883
- Contribution to the Community and Society: 0.887
- Job Satisfaction: 0.785
- Work Motivation: 0.881

All observed variables have Corrected Item-Total Correlation values greater than 0.3, and all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.6. Therefore, the scales demonstrate acceptable reliability and are suitable for subsequent analyses.

4.1.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

***Independent Variables**

In the initial round of EFA, items **DD6** and **MT4** were removed due to significant cross-loadings on multiple factors. A second round of EFA was subsequently conducted, yielding the following results:

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Independent Variables

"KMO and Bartlett's Test"		
"Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy."		.896
"Bartlett's Test of Sphericity"	Approx. Chi-Square"	16846.409
	df	741
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Results of the statistical test)

KMO = 0.896, indicating that factor analysis is appropriate. Sig. (Bartlett's Test) = 0.000 (sig. < 0.05), confirming that the observed variables are sufficiently correlated to proceed with EFA.

The EFA results reveal that six factors were extracted based on the eigenvalue criterion (eigenvalue = 3.174 > 1)." These six factors effectively summarize the information contained in the 42 observed variables included in the EFA.

The total variance explained by these factors is 61.286%, which exceeds the acceptable threshold of 50%. This indicates that the extracted factors account for 61.286% of the total variance in the dataset of 42 observed variables.

***Mediating Variable (Job Satisfaction)**

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test for the Mediating Variable

"Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy."		.899
"Bartlett's Test of Sphericity"	"Approx. Chi-Square"	2220.674
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Results of the statistical test)

KMO = 0.899 > 0.5, indicating that factor analysis is appropriate.

Sig. (Bartlett's Test) = 0.000 (sig. < 0.05), confirming that the observed variables are sufficiently correlated to justify the use of EFA.

The results from the rotated factor matrix indicate that one factor was extracted from the observed variables included in the EFA. The explained variance of this factor is 59.801%, based on an eigenvalue of 3.588 > 1.

***Dependent Variable (Work Motivation)**

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test for the Dependent Variable

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.919
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2800.637
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Results of the statistical test)

MO = 0.851 > 0.5, indicating that factor analysis is appropriate.

Sig. (Bartlett's Test) = 0.000 (sig. < 0.05), confirming that the observed variables are sufficiently correlated for EFA.

One factor was extracted based on the eigenvalue criterion (Eigenvalue = 4.116 > 1). The total variance explained by this factor is 58.805%, which exceeds the threshold of 50%.

Thus, the extracted factor accounts for 58.805% of the variance in the observed variables included in the EFA.

4.1.3. Scale Validation through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Following the EFA, with eight representative factors converging from the Pattern Matrix, the research team conducted Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to assess the model's goodness-of-fit to the data using Model Fit indices.

The results show that all Model Fit indices fall within acceptable or good thresholds:

- CMIN/DF = 1.960 < 3
- GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index) = 0.892 > 0.8
- CFI (Comparative Fit Index) = 0.948 > 0.9
- TLI (Tucker–Lewis Index) = 0.945 > 0.9
- RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) = 0.033 < 0.08
- PCLOSE = 1.000 > 0.05

These results indicate that the model has a good fit with the empirical data.

The Regression Weights table shows that all observed variables have p-values < 0.05, confirming that they are statistically significant in the model.

Moreover, all Standardized Regression Weights are greater than 0.5, indicating high factor loadings and unidimensionality.

The correlation test between latent variables (Table 4) demonstrates that all Composite Reliability (CR) values exceed 0.7, and all Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values exceed 0.5, ensuring convergent validity of the constructs.

Furthermore, the square root of each AVE is greater than the inter-construct correlations, and the Maximum Shared Variance (MSV) values are smaller than the AVE values.

These results confirm that the measurement model satisfies discriminant validity.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix and Convergent/Discriminant Validity of Latent Constructs

	CR	AVE	MSV	DL	DG	DT	CD	HL	TL	DD	MT
DL	0.884	0.522	0.484	0.723							
DG	0.891	0.539	0.230	0.480	0.734						
DT	0.884	0.522	0.193	0.353	0.242	0.722					
CD	0.888	0.531	0.215	0.383	0.095	0.094	0.729				
HL	0.867	0.523	0.484	0.696	0.465	0.439	0.464	0.723			
TL	0.879	0.549	0.107	0.327	0.102	-0.007	-0.001	0.291	0.741		
DD	0.879	0.550	0.124	0.353	0.173	0.127	0.082	0.260	0.133	0.741	
MT	0.878	0.546	0.142	0.377	0.052	0.041	0.179	0.321	0.040	0.079	0.739

(Source: Author's Analysis)

4.2. Model Testing and Hypothesis Verification

After confirming the model's suitability through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), the research team incorporated all validated observed and latent variables into the model to conduct.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and test the proposed hypotheses.

The results of the SEM analysis indicate the following model fit indices:

- CMIN/DF = 1.960 < 3
- GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index) = 0.892 > 0.8
- CFI (Comparative Fit Index) = 0.948 > 0.9
- TLI (Tucker–Lewis Index) = 0.945 > 0.9
- RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) = 0.033 < 0.08
- PCLOSE = 1.000 > 0.05

These values suggest that the empirical data fit the proposed model well.

The results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Results of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

(Source: Research Findings)

The Regression Weights table indicates that all observed variables have p-values < 0.05, demonstrating that all variables are statistically significant in the model.

The Standardized Regression Weights show that all factor loadings are greater than 0.5, indicating strong correlations between observed variables and their corresponding latent constructs, and confirming unidimensionality.

Table 5: Standardized Regression Weights – Direct Effects

	Estimate
DL <--- HL	.282
DL <--- TL	.191
DL <--- MT	.219
DL <--- DD	.165
DL <--- DG	.243
DL <--- DT	.127
DL <--- CD	.164

(Source: Research Findings)

The standardized regression estimates in Table 5 show that all six independent variables have a positive direct effect on the dependent variable (Work Motivation). In addition, the mediating variable (Job Satisfaction) also positively influences the dependent variable.

Table 6: Standardized Regression Weights – Indirect Effects

Indirect Path	Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	Lower	Upper	P-Value
TL --> HL --> DL	0.040	0.068	0.019	0.066	0.002
MT --> HL --> DL	0.044	0.060	0.018	0.077	0.003
DD --> HL --> DL	0.015	0.025	0.006	0.032	0.002
DG --> HL --> DL	0.060	0.086	0.029	0.096	0.003
DT --> HL --> DL	0.070	0.088	0.029	0.115	0.003
CD --> HL --> DL	0.085	0.102	0.036	0.139	0.003

(Source: Research Findings)

The p-values for all indirect relationships are less than 0.05, indicating that the mediated effects are statistically significant in the model.

The standardized regression weights in Table 6 show that all six independent variables have positive indirect effects on the dependent variable through the mediating variable. In other words, they positively influence job satisfaction, which in turn enhances work motivation.

4.3. Hypothesis Testing and Discussion of Research Findings

The results from Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), including hypothesis testing and analysis of group differences based on qualitative variables, indicate that all hypotheses were supported.

*Direct Effects on the Dependent Variable (Work Motivation)

The factors are ranked in descending order of standardized impact coefficients:

Performance Evaluation and Recognition (DG): $\beta = 0.243$: A one-unit increase in DG leads to a 0.243-unit increase in work motivation.

Working Environment (MT): $\beta = 0.219$: A one-unit improvement in MT leads to a 0.219 unit increase in work motivation.

Compensation (TL): $\beta = 0.191$: A one-unit increase in TL leads to a 0.191-unit increase in work motivation.

Job Characteristics (DD): $\beta = 0.165$: A one-unit improvement in DD leads to a 0.165 unit increase in work motivation.

Contribution to the Community and Society (CD): $\beta = 0.164$: A one-unit increase in CD leads to a 0.164-unit increase in work motivation.

Training and Promotion Opportunities (DT): $\beta = 0.127$: A one-unit improvement in DT leads to a 0.127 unit increase in work motivation.

***Indirect Effects via Job Satisfaction (HL)**

The following factors influence work motivation indirectly through job satisfaction, ranked by strength of impact:

Contribution to the Community and Society (CD): $\beta = 0.102$: A one-unit increase in CD leads to a 0.102 unit increase in work motivation via HL.

Training and Promotion Opportunities (DT): $\beta = 0.088$: A one-unit improvement in DT leads to a 0.088 unit increase in work motivation via HL.

Performance Evaluation and Recognition (DG): $\beta = 0.086$: A one-unit increase in DG leads to a 0.086 unit increase in work motivation via HL.

Compensation (TL): $\beta = 0.068$: A one-unit increase in TL leads to a 0.068-unit increase in work motivation via HL.

Working Environment (MT): $\beta = 0.060$: A one-unit improvement in MT leads to a 0.060 unit increase in work motivation via HL.

Job Characteristics (DD): $\beta = 0.025$: A one-unit improvement in DD leads to a 0.025 unit increase in work motivation via HL.

***Effect of the Mediating Variable**

The mediating variable **Job Satisfaction (HL)** has a standardized impact coefficient of $\beta = 0.282$: A one-unit increase in HL results in a 0.282-unit increase in work motivation (DL).

Table 7: R² Values

Variable	R ² Estimate
HL (Job Satisfaction)	0.608
DL (Work Motivation)	0.624

(Source: Research Findings)

The R² value for Job Satisfaction (HL) is 0.608, indicating that the independent variables explain 60.8% of its variance.

The R^2 value for Work Motivation (DL) is 0.624, meaning that the influencing factors explain 62.4% of its variance.

5. DISCUSSION ON REGRESSION RESULTS

The regression analysis—including both unstandardized and standardized coefficients—provides clear evidence for the relationships between organizational factors, **job satisfaction (HL)**, and **work motivation (DL)** of grassroots-level officials of the Vietnam Women's Union.

All direct paths in the model are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), with many showing high levels of significance ($p < 0.001$). These results confirm that factors such as **Compensation (TL)**, **Working Environment (MT)**, **Job Characteristics (DD)**, **Performance Evaluation and Recognition (DG)**, **Training and Promotion (DT)**, and **Contribution to the Community (CD)** significantly influence work motivation through the mediating role of job satisfaction.

In addition, all regression coefficients are positive, indicating **positive associations** between the constructs. That is, improvements in these organizational factors are likely to enhance both employee satisfaction and motivation.

(1) Direct Effects on Work Motivation (DL)

The results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis indicate that organizational factors have a statistically significant direct impact on the work motivation of grassroots-level staff of the Vietnam Women's Union. The standardized regression coefficients reveal the magnitude of the impact of each factor, listed in descending order:

Performance Evaluation and Recognition (DG): The standardized coefficient is 0.243, meaning that a one-unit increase in evaluation and recognition leads to a 0.243-unit increase in work motivation. This finding highlights the importance of timely and fair acknowledgment of staff efforts and achievements in promoting direct motivation. Hypothesis H4 is supported.

Work Environment (MT): The standardized coefficient is 0.219, suggesting that a one-unit improvement in the working environment results in a 0.219-unit increase in work motivation. A supportive, positive, and cooperative working environment clearly exerts a significant influence on staff morale and engagement. Hypothesis H2 is supported.

Compensation (TL): The standardized coefficient is 0.191. Although not the strongest factor, a reasonable compensation package still plays an important role in directly enhancing motivation. Hypothesis H1 is supported.

Job Characteristics (DD): The coefficient is 0.165. Improvements in job characteristics (e.g., multidisciplinary nature, flexibility) lead to a 0.165-unit increase in work motivation, indicating a moderate but meaningful influence. Hypothesis H3 is supported.

Contribution to Community and Society (CD): With a coefficient of 0.164, this factor reflects strong intrinsic motivation driven by the meaningfulness of the job. Hypothesis H6 is supported.

Training and Advancement Opportunities (DT): The lowest direct impact among the group, at 0.127, but still significant. Offering development opportunities contributes to enhanced motivation. Hypothesis H5 is supported.

Additionally, Job Satisfaction (HL) has a strong direct effect on work motivation ($\beta = 0.282$). This affirms that satisfied staff members are more motivated to perform their duties, emphasizing the pivotal role of job satisfaction in transforming organizational conditions into real motivational outcomes. Hypothesis H13 is supported.

(2) Indirect Effects on Work Motivation (DL) via Job Satisfaction (HL)

A Bootstrap analysis with 2,000 samples was conducted to examine the mediating role of job satisfaction (HL) in the relationship between independent factors and work motivation (DL). All indirect effects were statistically significant with p-values < 0.05 . The 95% confidence intervals for these effects did not include zero, confirming their reliability.

The magnitudes of the indirect effects through job satisfaction, as presented in Table 6, are ranked as follows:

Contribution to Community and Society (CD) \rightarrow HL \rightarrow DL: The indirect effect is 0.102, the strongest among the variables. This suggests that when staff perceive their work as contributing to the community, their job satisfaction increases significantly, leading to stronger work motivation. This underscores the strategic importance of job meaningfulness and social impact as motivational drivers. Hypothesis H12 is supported.

Training and Advancement Opportunities (DT) \rightarrow HL \rightarrow DL: The indirect effect is 0.088. Opportunities for learning and career development not only directly influence motivation but also indirectly enhance it through improved job satisfaction. Hypothesis H11 is supported.

Performance Evaluation and Recognition (DG) \rightarrow HL \rightarrow DL: The indirect effect is 0.086. A timely and fair recognition system enhances job satisfaction, which in turn indirectly boosts motivation. Hypothesis H10 is supported.

Compensation (TL) \rightarrow HL \rightarrow DL: The indirect effect is 0.068. Although lower in magnitude, a fair compensation policy contributes to satisfaction and, consequently, work motivation. Hypothesis H7 is supported.

Work Environment (MT) \rightarrow HL \rightarrow DL: The indirect effect is 0.060. A positive and supportive environment increases satisfaction and thus indirectly enhances motivation. Hypothesis H8 is supported.

Job Characteristics (DD) \rightarrow HL \rightarrow DL: The indirect effect is 0.025, the lowest among the factors. Nevertheless, suitable job characteristics still contribute to higher satisfaction and thereby promote motivation. Hypothesis H9 is supported.

In summary, job satisfaction is not only an independent factor but also a critical mediator that transforms organizational conditions, policies, and job values into genuine intrinsic motivation for grassroots-level Women's Union staff.

6. SOLUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS TO ENHANCE WORK MOTIVATION OF GRASSROOTS-LEVEL STAFF OF THE VIETNAM WOMEN'S UNION IN THE RED RIVER DELTA

6.1. Proposed Solutions

6.1.1. Improving Working Conditions and the Work Environment

The research demonstrates that the working environment (MT) has a positive and statistically significant impact on the work motivation (DL) of grassroots-level staff of the Vietnam Women's Union. This is evidenced by both direct and indirect effects:

Direct impact: The standardized regression weight from MT to DL is $\beta = 0.219$, indicating that a supportive, comfortable, and collaborative work environment directly enhances staff motivation. When staff feel supported by colleagues and supervisors and are provided with adequate physical space, they are more likely to work enthusiastically and proactively.

Indirect impact via job satisfaction (HL): The work environment also indirectly influences motivation through job satisfaction. Specifically, MT significantly affects HL ($\beta = 0.211$), and in turn, HL strongly impacts DL ($\beta = 0.282$). This creates a causal chain: a better working environment \rightarrow increased satisfaction \rightarrow higher motivation. The indirect effect ($\beta = 0.060$) is statistically significant, reinforcing the critical role of the working environment.

In practice, many grassroots VWU units, especially in remote areas, face difficulties such as a lack of private offices, outdated equipment, and poor infrastructure. As of 2024, around 7% of grassroots units still lacked internet-connected computers, impeding communication and management.

Recommended solutions include:

- Provide minimum essential equipment and mobilize resources through socialization.
- Enhance digital literacy and skills in office software, social media, and online conferencing.
- Improve workspace infrastructure (lighting, internet, utilities).
- Create a supportive, cohesive, community-oriented work culture.
- Integrate infrastructure investment into the medium-term public investment plan.

Improving working conditions will not only foster staff retention but also elevate the operational effectiveness of the Union.

6.1.2. Incentive Policies and Recognition of Contributions

The research reveals that performance evaluation and recognition (DG) significantly affect staff motivation, both directly and indirectly:

- Direct effect: DG → DL has a standardized regression weight of 0.243, one of the strongest effects among all factors, second only to job satisfaction. Transparent and fair performance evaluations and positive feedback enhance staff engagement and commitment.
- Indirect effect: DG also indirectly affects DL via HL, with $\beta = 0.086$ ($p < 0.05$), confirming that recognition enhances satisfaction and subsequently fosters intrinsic motivation.

In the context of ongoing organizational restructuring, performance appraisal is not only a human resource management tool but also a mechanism to retain committed staff.

Recommended actions:

- Increase allowances for grassroots VWU staff, especially in disadvantaged areas.
- Establish a dedicated reward system for part-time staff.
- Create honor titles at district/provincial levels for outstanding staff.
- Offer create clear pathways for professional progression for top performers.
- Develop a mechanism to identify and train future leaders for higher positions.

Reasonable incentives and acknowledgment of contributions are key to staff retention and motivation.

6.1.3. Capacity Building and Career Advancement Opportunities

Training and promotion opportunities (DT) have a moderate yet meaningful impact on work motivation:

Direct effect: DT → DL has a standardized weight of 0.127, relatively modest compared to other factors.

Indirect effect via HL: DT has a notable indirect impact through job satisfaction, with $\beta = 0.088$, ranking second among indirect effects.

This indicates that when staff perceive investment in their personal growth and skill development, their satisfaction and internal motivation increase significantly.

Recommended solutions:

- Develop a structured training roadmap, including soft skills and digital tools.
- Establish cost-effective, flexible online learning platforms.
- Facilitate international training opportunities.
- Design career development pathways within the political system.

- Promote Party membership among local chapter leaders to elevate their influence and leadership potential.

Capacity building and career prospects will help enhance work quality and strengthen long-term staff engagement.

6.1.4. Building Pride and Public Service Motivation

Among the examined factors, contribution to the community and society (CD) emerged as the most profound influence on motivation:

- Direct effect: CD → DL with a standardized weight of 0.164.
- Indirect effect via HL: CD → HL → DL with $\beta = 0.102$ – the strongest among all indirect paths.

This highlights that when staff recognize the social value of their work, such as empowering vulnerable women, supporting families, and promoting gender equality, they experience pride, satisfaction, and enhanced motivation.

Recommended solutions:

- Integrate traditional education and organizational pride into training programs.
- Promote outstanding VWU staff via internal and external communication.
- Organize forums, award ceremonies, and peer-sharing events.

Cultivating a sense of pride and mission not only increases commitment but also enhances performance and leadership in community engagement.

6.2. Recommendations

6.2.1. Recommendations to the Government

To support the sustainable development of grassroots VWU under Resolution No. 18-NQ/TW, the Government should implement:

- Human resources and transfer policies: Clearly define positions, criteria, and allowances for grassroots VWU leaders, especially the dual-role Chairwoman–Vice Chair of the Fatherland Front post-July 1, 2025. Develop planning and appointment frameworks for staff in disadvantaged areas.
- Financial policies and incentives: Increase allowances and operational support; encourage resource mobilization through socialized funding and corporate/community sponsorship.
- Digital transformation and IT infrastructure: Invest in digital tools at the commune level to support member management, online meetings, and distance learning; integrate gender equality training for civil servants.
- Youth leadership development: Offer scholarships and short-term training for promising female leaders; enhance political participation and multitasking capabilities.

- Performance evaluation and institutionalization: Implement a KPI system for assessing VWU performance, serving as a basis for rewards and policy adjustments to ensure fairness and transparency.

An integrated, flexible policy framework is essential to empower VWU staff and modernize grassroots political institutions.

6.2.2. Recommendations to the Grassroots-level Vietnam Fatherland Front

In the organizational restructuring process under Resolution No. 18-NQ/TW, the Fatherland Front should:

- Preserve the relative independence of the VWU to maintain its gender representation function.
- Support the VWU in planning and implementing specialized programs (e.g., gender equality, anti-domestic violence, women's entrepreneurship).
- Ensure financial and operational autonomy via separate budget lines.
- Retain the VWU's legal status as an independent organization, not just a sub-unit or task force.
- Safeguard the Union's right to social criticism and policy recommendations, especially in supervision programs.
- Cooperate in revising Regulation No. 80-QĐ/TW to clearly define the VWU's role in personnel recommendations, particularly for dual-role leaders.
- Establish a post-merger oversight mechanism to ensure the practical implementation of autonomy commitments.

6.2.3. Recommendations to the Central Vietnam Women's Union

In implementing Resolution No. 18-NQ/TW on streamlining the political system, the Central VWU should proactively restructure its organizational model and innovate its operations to adapt to dual-role leadership at the grassroots level post-July 1, 2025.

Key areas of focus:

- Organizational structure: Retain gender representation; develop adaptive models for diverse local contexts; guide personnel structures for expanded communes.
- Human resource policy: Standardize recruitment criteria; reallocate staff post-merger; advocate for institutional pathways to recruit VWU staff into local political systems.
- Training and development: Build capacity-building programs for emerging female leaders; establish online learning platforms; expand access to domestic and international training.
- Digital transformation: Develop a nationwide member database; create membership management software and mobile apps; advance data-driven governance.

- Emulation and inspiration: Adapt reward criteria to the new context; launch communication campaigns; build the image of resilient, innovative, community-oriented VWU staff.

Implementation roadmap:

- Q3/2025–Q2/2026: Preparation and institutional shaping.
- Q3/2026–2027: Pilot phase.
- From 2028 onwards: National scale-up based on proven effectiveness.

7. CONCLUSION

This study contributes to clarifying the factors influencing the work motivation of grassroots-level officials of the Vietnam Women’s Union in the Red River Delta region, grounded in a robust theoretical framework and supported by reliable empirical evidence. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the results indicate that all six factors—compensation (TL), working environment (MT), job characteristics (DD), performance evaluation and recognition (DG), training and promotion opportunities (DT), and contribution to the community and society (CD)—positively affect work motivation, both directly and indirectly through the mediating role of job satisfaction.

Among these, performance evaluation and recognition (DG) exert the strongest direct impact, highlighting the central role of fair and timely acknowledgment in encouraging staff commitment and engagement.

Notably, contribution to the community and society (CD) demonstrated the most significant indirect effect through job satisfaction, reflecting the importance of public service motivation among grassroots Women’s Union staff.

The practical implication is that enhancing work motivation in a sustainable manner requires a comprehensive approach: improving working conditions, ensuring fair compensation, expanding opportunities for professional development, and especially reinforcing a sense of pride and purpose through the recognition of social value in their work.

The recommendations provided to the Government, the Vietnam Fatherland Front, and the Central Women’s Union emphasize the need to institutionalize mechanisms that guarantee the autonomy, role, and resources of the Union following organizational restructuring, thereby maintaining and strengthening its operational effectiveness.

The findings not only enrich the theoretical understanding of public sector motivation in Vietnam but also offer practical insights for policy formulation and human resource development strategies aimed at empowering women and promoting sustainable development and social progress

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